

Engineering Transport Properties of Fibrous Materials

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Abstract

Fibrous materials have wide applications in many different fields including filtration, fuel cells, thermal insulation, tissue engineering, paper products and apparel. In most of these applications, it is essential to optimize the transport properties. In this paper, the principle mechanisms of different transport phenomena in fibrous media as well as their interactions are explained. The effects of various material parameters on the transport properties are discussed. Specific models for heat transfer through penguin feathers and water transport through branching tree network are presented. The theoretical understandings are applied to develop new fibrous materials for functional clothing. Furthermore, novel instruments developed in our group to characterize the transport properties of fibrous materials are presented.

INTRODUCTION

Fibrous materials have wide applications in many different fields including filtration, fuel cells, thermal insulation, tissue engineering, paper products and apparel products. In most of these applications, fibrous materials serve as media, through which air, vapor, particles, heat, photons or electrons pass through. It is therefore essential to understand the transport phenomena within fibrous media so as to optimize the transport properties of fibrous materials for specific applications.

MODELING

Based on the improved understanding of the mechanisms, we have developed a transient model of coupled heat and moisture transfer with thermal radiation and phase change [1, 2 and 3]. Figure 1 shows the model heat and mass transport through fibrous materials.

Fig. 1 Schematic Diagram of Heat & Mass Transport Through Fibrous Materials

This model was used to analyze the effects of various material parameters on the transport properties. The model has also been used to predict the optimum porosity [4] and porosity distributions [5] of fibrous materials for thermal insulation. Figure 2 shows the optimum porosity distribution.

Fig.2 Typical optimum porosity distribution of non-uniform fibrous insulation

Considering the superior thermal insulation performance of penguin downs, the geometric features of penguin downs were analyzed and the heat transfer through penguin downs was modeled [6]. It is understood that the special geometric features of penguin downs are responsible for the superior insulation. Figure 3 shows the model of heat transfer through penguin downs.

Figure 3 Model of heat transfer through penguin downs.

Trees have a superior water transport network, which allows the fast transmission of water from the roots to the leaf top. The understanding of this mechanism can lead to the development of super moisture management fabrics. A theoretical model of water transport through branching tree network was also developed, which can explain the growth of tree height [7].

ENGINEERING FIBROUS MATERIALS

The improved understandings have been applied to develop new fibrous materials for functional clothing. These include the reflective superfine fibres for shielding radiation [8, 9], but little change in moisture vapor permeability, the plant structured fabrics [10], which emulating the branching network of the trees, and nanofibrous scaffolds for artificial blood vessels [11].

CHARACTERIZATION OF TRANSPORT PROPERTIES OF FIBROUS MATERIALS

The validity of the theoretical models and the performance of novel fibrous materials should be validated through experimental measurements. Specific novel instruments have been developed for these purposes. These include the Transplanar Water Transport Tester [12], the Sweating Guided Hotplate for subzero conditions [13] and the sweating fabric manikin-Walter [14].

CONCLUSIONS

The transport phenomena in fibrous materials are complex processes. The understanding and modeling of these processes can lead to the optimization and innovation of new fibrous materials. Further work is required in this area. One of

such work is the modeling and engineering of fibrous materials with differential transport properties [15].

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